

Role of Serum Alkaline Phosphatase in Osteopenia of Premature Infants

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Abstract

Background: Osteopenia, a condition indicative of reduced bone mineral content, is commonly observed among premature neonates. Early detection is crucial to initiate timely interventions and reduce the risk of long-term skeletal complications. Identifying reliable biochemical markers may enhance prediction and management strategies. **Aim of the Study:** The aim of this study was to assess whether serum alkaline phosphatase (ALP) levels can be used to predict osteopenia in premature infants. **Patients and Methods:** An observational cross-sectional study was conducted at the Neonatal Intensive Care Units of Baghdad Teaching Hospital and Children Welfare Teaching Hospital in Baghdad, Iraq. The study spanned six months, from October 1, 2024, to March 31, 2025. A total of 100 premature infants were enrolled. Osteopenia diagnosis was made by a senior pediatrician based on radiographic findings and supporting investigations. Serum ALP levels were measured twice during hospitalization. **Results:** Osteopenia was identified in 17% (17/100) of the premature infants. Infants diagnosed with osteopenia had significantly shorter gestational age and lower birth weight compared to those without the condition. Additionally, ALP levels in both the first and second samples were significantly elevated among osteopenic infants. Other associated factors included premature rupture of membranes and low Apgar scores at both one and five minutes after birth. **Conclusions:** Elevated serum alkaline phosphatase levels serve as a significant biochemical marker for predicting osteopenia in premature neonates. This marker may aid clinicians in early identification and management of at-risk infants.

Introduction

Osteoporosis and osteopenia are significant yet often under-recognized complications in premature neonates, primarily due to inadequate postnatal calcium and phosphorus intake. In preterm infants, these minerals, crucial for skeletal mineralization, are found in suboptimal amounts in breast milk, especially when compared to the mineral accretion that typically occurs in the third trimester of gestation [1]. Approximately 80% of fetal mineral accumulation happens during this critical period, which is often missed in cases of premature birth [2]. Consequently, osteopenia of prematurity (OOP)—also referred to as metabolic bone disease of prematurity (MBDP)—is commonly observed in neonatal intensive care units

(NICUs), particularly among very low birth weight (VLBW) and extremely low birth weight (ELBW) infants [3]. The mother is the primary source of mineral transfer in fetal life, facilitated by active placental transport mechanisms that ensure adequate fetal serum levels of calcium, phosphate, and magnesium [4]. Hormones such as parathyroid hormone (PTH), parathyroid hormone-related peptide (PTHrP), calcitonin, and vitamin D [33] also play essential roles in maintaining fetal mineral balance [5]. At birth, this placental supply is abruptly interrupted by umbilical cord clamping, causing a significant shift in mineral homeostasis. Postnatal adaptations, including renal and gastrointestinal maturation, are often delayed in premature infants, making them particularly vulnerable

More Information

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to mineral imbalances and bone demineralization [4]. OOP is typically asymptomatic in its early stages; with signs such as fractures or chest wall instability only becoming apparent in advanced disease. Radiographic signs of demineralization may take several weeks to emerge, often appearing between 5 and 11 weeks of postnatal age [6]. Therefore, early biochemical screening is essential. Among the various biochemical markers, serum alkaline phosphatase (ALP) has emerged as a valuable indicator of bone turnover and impaired mineralization [7]. Although ALP levels physiologically increase during the first weeks of life, values exceeding 500 IU/L are suggestive of poor bone mineralization, while levels above 700–900 IU/L are strongly associated with OOP, particularly when paired with hypophosphatemia [7]. Still, ALP interpretation requires caution due to its elevation in liver and gastrointestinal diseases, which may confound its diagnostic utility [8]. Various antenatal and postnatal factors increase the risk for OOP. Antenatal contributors include intrauterine growth restriction, preeclampsia, and placental insufficiency, all of which impair mineral transfer [3,9]. Postnatally, the prolonged use of parenteral nutrition (PN), especially without adequate mineral supplementation, the use of diuretics or corticosteroids, and conditions like necrotizing enterocolitis and bronchopulmonary dysplasia further exacerbate mineral depletion [10,11]. Despite the high incidence and potential morbidity—including increased fracture risk, ventilator dependence, and impaired growth—there is no universal consensus on screening protocols, diagnostic cut-offs, or management strategies for OOP [12,13]. Given these concerns, early identification through accessible and reliable biochemical markers is critical. ALP has been recognized as a potentially effective predictor for OOP due to its role in bone metabolism. This study aims to evaluate the clinical utility of serum ALP levels as a predictive marker for osteopenia in premature neonates to facilitate timely diagnosis and intervention, ultimately improving skeletal outcomes and reducing long-term complications in this vulnerable population.

Method

This observational cross-sectional study was conducted over a six-month period, from October 1, 2024, to March 31, 2025, in the Neonatal Intensive Care Units (NICUs) of Baghdad Teaching Hospital and Children Welfare Teaching Hospital Medical Complex in Baghdad, Iraq. The study aimed to assess the predictive value of serum alkaline phosphatase (ALP) levels for osteopenia in premature infants. The study population included all premature neonates admitted to the NICUs during the study period. A total of 100 premature infants were selected through convenience sampling after verifying eligibility based on inclusion and

exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria were neonatal age, both genders, gestational age less than 31 weeks, and birth weight below 1500 grams. Infants were excluded if they had postnatal age, congenital anomalies, congenital heart disease, perinatal asphyxia, were deceased, transferred to another department, or if parental consent was denied. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed by the study supervisor. Information was obtained directly from the mothers and patient records. Collected data included demographic and clinical characteristics, delivery mode, maternal comorbidities, antenatal steroid use, premature rupture of membranes (PROM), total parenteral nutrition (TPN), and Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes. Laboratory parameters included hemoglobin, hematocrit, white blood cell count, serum calcium, phosphate (SPO₄), ALP, and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels. Osteopenia diagnosis was based on clinical assessment, radiological findings, and laboratory investigations, conducted by a senior pediatrician. Gestational age was determined using the New Ballard Score. Blood samples were collected twice: upon NICU admission and one week later. Ethical approval was obtained from the Arab Board of Health Specializations, with institutional permissions and informed oral parental consent secured. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 22. Descriptive statistics, chi-square test, independent sample t-test, Pearson correlation, and ROC curve analysis were applied. A p -value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

This study included one hundred premature infants admitted with mean gestational age of (29.3 weeks) and mean birth weight of (1.2 Kg). Osteopenia was detected in 17 (17%) premature infants. (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Prevalence of Osteopenia among Premature Infants

No significant differences were observed between premature infants with osteopenia and premature infants without osteopenia regarding gender ($p=0.8$).

Mean gestational age was significantly shorter among infants with osteopenia (p=0.004). Mean birth weight

was significantly lower among infants with osteopenia (p<0.001). (Table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of Demographic Characteristics According to Osteopenia Prevalence

Variable	Study groups				P
	No osteopenia		Osteopenia		
	No.	%	No.	%	
Gender					0.8*NS
Male	22	26.5	5	29.4	
Female	61	73.5	12	70.6	
Gestational age					0.004**S
Mean±SD (weeks)	29.6±2.3		27.7±2.6		
Birth weight					<0.001**S
Mean±SD (Kg)	1.28±0.19		1.09±0.21		

*Chi square test, **Independent sample t-test, S=Significant, NS=Not significant.

No significant differences were observed between premature infants with osteopenia and premature infants without osteopenia regarding delivery mode (p=0.8), maternal clinical co-morbidity (p=0.1), steroids history (p=0.17) and total parenteral nutrition (p=0.8).

There was a highly significant association between positive maternal PROM and infants with osteopenia (p<0.001). Means of apgar scores after 1 & 5 minutes were significantly lower among infants with osteopenia (p<0.001). (Table 2).

Table 2: Distribution of General Characteristics According to Osteopenia Prevalence

Variable	Study groups				P
	No osteopenia		Osteopenia		
	No.	%	No.	%	
Delivery mode					0.8*NS
NVD	27	32.5	9	52.9	
CS	56	67.5	8	47.1	
Maternal clinical co-morbidity					0.1*NS
Yes	34	41.0	10	58.8	
No	49	59.0	7	41.2	
Steroids history					0.17*NS
Positive	42	50.6	10	58.8	
Negative	41	49.4	7	41.2	
PROM					<0.001*S
Yes	17	20.5	13	76.5	
No	66	79.5	4	23.5	
Total preteral nutrition					0.8**NS
Mean±SD (day)	6.4±2.9		5.1±1.2		
Apgar score after 1 minute					<0.001**S
Mean±SD	4.5±0.8		3.4±1.6		
Apgar score after 5 minutes					<0.001**S
Mean±SD	7.5±1		6±2.4		

Note: *Chi square test, **Independent sample t-test, S=Significant, NS=Not significant.

No significant differences were observed between premature infants with osteopenia and infants without osteopenia regarding 1st sample Hb (p=0.06), 1st sample HCT (p=0.18) and 1st sample WBC count (p=0.3). Means of 2nd sample Hb, HCT and WBC count were significantly

lower among infants with osteopenia (p<0.001). Means of Hb, HCT and WBC count differences were significantly higher among infants with osteopenia (p<0.001). (Table 3).

Table 3: Distribution of Hematological Investigations According to Osteopenia Prevalence

Variable	Study groups		P
	No osteopenia	Osteopenia	
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	
Hemoglobin level (g/dl)			
1 st sample	14.3±2.7	12.9±2.8	0.06*NS
2 nd sample	12.6±2.1	7.3±2	<0.001* ^S
Difference	1.7±2.3	5.6±0.44	<0.001* ^S
HCT (%)			
1 st sample	42.1±8.2	39.2±8.8	0.18*NS
2 nd sample	37±6.1	29.2±6	<0.001* ^S
Difference	5.1±6.8	10±3.8	0.005* ^S
WBC count (x10³)			
1 st sample	9.7±6.1	8.1±2.9	0.3*NS
2 nd sample	11.1±6.4	5.7±2.6	0.001* ^S
Difference	-1.4±4.3	2.4±4.4	0.001* ^S

Note: *Independent sample t-test, S=Significant, NS=Not significant.

No significant differences were observed between premature infants with osteopenia and premature infants without osteopenia regarding calcium tests ($p>0.05$) and SPO_4 tests ($p>0.05$). Means of serum ALP levels at 1st and 2nd samples count were significantly

higher among infants with osteopenia ($p=0.001$, $p<0.001$, respectively). Mean of serum ALP level difference was significantly higher among infants with osteopenia ($p<0.001$). (Table 4).

Table 4: Distribution of Serum Investigations According to Osteopenia Prevalence

Variable	Study groups		P
	No osteopenia	Osteopenia	
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	
Serum calcium level (mg/dl)			
1 st sample	7.9±1	8.1±0.7	0.6*NS
2 nd sample	8.2±0.9	7.8±0.9	0.07*NS
Difference	-0.23±0.7	-0.08±0.16	0.3*NS
Serum ALP level (IU/L)			
1 st sample	216.5±71.3	270.5±30.7	0.001* ^S
2 nd sample	242.2±63.3	415.3±16.9	<0.001* ^S
Difference	-25.7±71.2	-244.8±39.7	<0.001* ^S
Serum SPO₄ level (mg/dl)			
1 st sample	5.6±0.4	5.58±0.5	0.9*NS
2 nd sample	5.58±0.6	5.5±0.4	0.7*NS
Difference	0.01±0.6	0.05±0.5	0.7*NS

Note: *Independent sample t-test, S=Significant, NS=Not significant.

No significant differences were observed between premature infants with osteopenia and premature

infants without osteopenia regarding 1st and 2nd CRP levels ($p>0.05$). (Table 5).

Table 5: Distribution of CRP Level According to Osteopenia Prevalence

Variable	Study groups				P
	No osteopenia		Osteopenia		
	No.	%	No.	%	
1 st sample CRP					0.5*NS

Positive	3	3.6	0	-	
Negative	80	96.4	17	100.0	
2nd sample CRP					0.2**NS
Yes	20	24.1	7	41.2	
No	63	75.9	10	58.8	

Note: * Fishers exact test, **Chi square test, NS=Not significant.

As shown in table 6 and figure 2; the serum ALP appropriate cutoff value in prediction of osteopenia among premature infants was (390 IU/L) with acceptable validity findings (sensitivity 100%, specificity 96.4% and accuracy 98%).

Table 6: Serum ALP Levels Predicting Osteopenia

Serum ALP (IU/L)	Sensitivity	Specificity	Accuracy
325	100%	91.6%	95%
390	100%	96.4%	98%
405	61.2%	100%	82%

Figure 2: ROC Curve of Serum ALP Level in Prediction of Osteopenia (AUC=0.99)

Table 7: Correlation between Hemoglobin Level of Infants and 1st Sample Serum ALP Level

Variable	1 st sample ALP (IU/L)
Gestational age	r=0.02
	P=0.8
Birth weight	r=0.14
	P=0.15
Hb level	r=-0.2
	P=0.04
Variable	2 nd sample ALP (IU/L)
Gestational age	r=0.07
	P=0.4
Birth weight	r=0.09
	P=0.3
Hb level	r=0.56
	P<0.001

As shown in table 7; there was a negative significant correlation between hemoglobin level of infants and 1st sample serum ALP level (r=0.2, p=0.04). There was a

positive highly significant correlation between hemoglobin level of infants and 2nd sample serum ALP level (r=0.56, p<0.001).

Discussion

Osteopenia is a prevalent condition in premature infants, often resulting from inadequate mineral accretion due to early birth. Its clinical relevance has increased with improved survival rates of preterm infants, largely due to advances in neonatal intensive care [14]. In this study, osteopenia was detected in 17% of the premature infants, a figure comparable to that reported by Abdallah et al. (13.3%) in a prospective Egyptian study [15], but lower than the 38% prevalence of rickets reported by Abdulla et al. in Iraq [16] and the 28% reported by Afroz et al. in Bangladesh [17]. Conversely, our prevalence was higher than the 12.3% found in a study by Carsi-Bocanegra et al. in Mexico [18]. These variations may be attributed to differences in nutritional protocols, gestational ages, sample sizes, and healthcare standards across regions [19]. Our study demonstrated a significantly shorter mean gestational age among infants with osteopenia (p=0.004), aligning with findings from Perrone et al. [20] and Ali et al. [21], who also identified prematurity as a key risk factor. Dombrovski et al. emphasized that premature infants often have immature bone metabolism, which impairs mineralization [22]. Similarly, we observed significantly lower birth weights among osteopenic infants (p<0.001), supporting results from Nare et al., who linked low birth weight with increased risk of metabolic bone disease [23]. A notable association was found between osteopenia and maternal premature rupture of membranes (PROM) (p<0.001) [34], echoing the findings of Perrone et al. [20]. Lower Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes were also significantly associated with osteopenia (p<0.001), consistent with studies by Cross et al. [24] and Graça et al. [25], suggesting that perinatal distress may influence bone health. Our analysis revealed significantly higher hemoglobin, hematocrit, and WBC counts in osteopenic infants (p<0.001), similar to observations by Ye et al. [26], who highlighted the link between hematological profiles and bone health. Li et al. also supported the role of bone in hematopoiesis [27]. A key finding was the significantly higher serum ALP levels at both time points among osteopenic infants (p=0.001, p<0.001), and the overall ALP difference was also significant (p<0.001), consistent with results by Abdallah et al. [15] and Saleem et al. [28]. Elevated ALP may indicate increased bone

turnover secondary to demineralization [29]. Zhang et al. [30] advocated ALP screening in ELBW infants, while Angelika et al. [29] linked ALP with multiple osteopenia risk factors. Interestingly, serum calcium and phosphate levels did not differ significantly between groups ($p>0.05$), aligning with Abdallah et al. [15], though other studies suggest combined use of SPO4 and ALP for screening [31]. Our ROC analysis found ALP cutoff value of 390 IU/L had high sensitivity (100%) and specificity (96.4%), comparable to Paul et al. (352.5 IU/L) and Abdallah et al. (500 IU/L) [15,31]. This supports the utility of ALP in screening and diagnosing osteopenia in premature infants [32].

Conclusion

Serum alkaline phosphatase (ALP) level is a strong predictor of osteopenia in premature infants. An ALP level of 390 IU/L showed high validity in detecting osteopenia. Osteopenia is significantly associated with short gestational age and low birth weight. Premature rupture of membranes and low Apgar scores also contribute to the risk. Abnormal hematological parameters were linked to osteopenia in these infants.

References

- [1] Chinoy A, Mughal MZ, Padidela R. Metabolic bone disease of prematurity: causes, recognition, prevention, treatment and long-term consequences. *Arch Dis Child Fetal Neonatal Ed.* 2019;104(5):F560–F566.
- [2] Sethi A, Priyadarshi M, Agarwal R, editors. Mineral and bone physiology in the foetus, preterm and full-term neonates. *Semin Fetal Neonatal Med.* 2019;24(5):101036.
- [3] Rustico SE, Calabria AC, Garber SJ. Metabolic bone disease of prematurity. *J Clin Transl Endocrinol.* 2014;1(3):85–91.
- [4] Mimouni FB, Mandel D, Lubetzky R, Senterre T. Calcium, phosphorus, magnesium and vitamin D requirements of the preterm infant. *World Rev Nutr Diet.* 2014;110:140–151.
- [5] Kovacs CS. Calcium, phosphorus, and bone metabolism in the fetus and newborn. *Early Hum Dev.* 2015;91:623–628.
- [6] Mitchell SM, Rogers SP, Hicks PD, Hawthorne KM, Parker BR, Abrams SA. High frequencies of elevated alkaline phosphatase activity and rickets exist in extremely low birth weight infants despite current nutritional support. *BMC Pediatr.* 2010;9:47.
- [7] Hung YL, Chen PC, Jeng SF, Hsieh CJ, Peng SS, Yen RF, et al. Serial measurements of serum alkaline phosphatase for early prediction of osteopaenia in preterm infants. *J Paediatr Child Health.* 2011;47:134–139.
- [8] Angelika R, Etika M, Mapindra MP. Associated neonatal and maternal factors of osteopenia of prematurity in low resource setting: a cross-sectional study. *Ann Med Surg (Lond).* 2021;64:102235.
- [9] Funke S, Morava E, Czakó M, Vida G, Ertl T, Kosztolányi G. Influence of genetic polymorphisms on bone disease of preterm infants. *Pediatr Res.* 2016;60:607–612.
- [10] Mimouni FB, Mandel D, Lubetzky R, Senterre T. Calcium, phosphorus, magnesium and vitamin D requirements of the preterm infant. *World Rev Nutr Diet.* 2014;110:140–151.
- [11] Brunetti G, Faienza MF, Piacente L, Ventura A, Oranger A, Carbone C, et al. High dickkopf-1 levels in sera and leukocytes from children with 21-hydroxylase deficiency on chronic glucocorticoid treatment. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab.* 2013;304:E546–554.
- [12] Angelika R, Etika M, Mapindra MP. Associated neonatal and maternal factors of osteopenia of prematurity in low resource setting: a cross-sectional study. *Ann Med Surg (Lond).* 2021;64:102235.
- [13] Chen W, Yang C, Chen H. Risk factors analysis and prevention of metabolic bone disease of prematurity. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2018;97:e12861.
- [14] Torró-Ferrero G, Fernández-Rego FJ, Gómez-Conesa A. Physical therapy to prevent osteopenia in preterm infants: A systematic review. *Children (Basel).* 2021;8(8):664.
- [15] Abdallah EAA, Said RN, Mosallam DS, Moawad EMI, Kamal NM, Fathallah MGE. Serial serum alkaline phosphatase as an early biomarker for osteopenia of prematurity. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2016;95(37):e4837.
- [16] Abdulla AI, Jumaah LF, Ibrahim HM. Prevalence of rickets regarding to maturity in children less than 3 years old attending Tikrit Teaching Hospital. *Med J Tikrit Univ.* 2019;25(1):82–92.
- [17] Afroz N, Chowdhury MA, Hoque M, Khan DA. Osteopenia in premature infants and effect of supplementation. *Bangladesh J Child Health.* 2015;39(3):135–140.
- [18] Carsi-Bocanegra EE, Frausto-Cárdenas OY, Aguilar-Quiñones GC. Incidence of osteopenia in premature newborns of less than 34 weeks' gestation in a neonatal intensive care unit. *Perinatol Reprod Hum.* 2014;28(4):193–197.
- [19] Harrison CM, Johnson K, McKechnie E. Osteopenia of prematurity: a national survey and review of practice. *Acta Paediatr.* 2008;97(4):407–413.
- [20] Perrone S, Caporilli C, Grassi F, Ferrocino M, Biagi E, Dell'Orto V, et al. Prenatal and neonatal bone health: updated review on early identification of newborns at high risk for osteopenia. *Nutrients.* 2023;15(16):3515.
- [21] Ali E, Rockman-Greenberg C, Moffatt M, Narvey M, Reed M, Jiang D. Caffeine is a risk factor for osteopenia of prematurity in preterm infants: a cohort study. *BMC Pediatr.* 2018;18(1):9.
- [22] Dombrowski FMOS, Méndez CKI, Vargas DM. Occurrence of metabolic bone disease in very low birth

weight preterm infants hospitalized in neonatal ICU. *Arq Catarin Med.* 2019;2(48):12–20.

[23] Nare R, Sawant VD, Surve R. Profile of metabolic bone disease in extremely low birth weight (ELBW) and very low birth weight (VLBW) neonates. *Egypt Pediatr Assoc Gaz.* 2024;72:25. doi: 10.1186/s43054-024-00268-0

[24] Cross B, Vasquez E. Osteopenia of prematurity prevention and treatment. *Internet J Emerg Intensive Care Med.* 2010;5(1):12–19.

[25] Graça MI, Silva J, Guimarães H. Metabolic bone disease of prematurity – a report of five cases. *J Pediatr Neonat Individual Med.* 2019;8(1):e080120.

[26] Ye X, Jiang H, Wang Y, Ji Y, Jiang X. A correlative studies between osteoporosis and blood cell composition: implications for auxiliary diagnosis of osteoporosis. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2020;99(26):e20864.

[27] Li Y, Hao W, Guan J, Li B, Meng L, Sun S, et al. Relationship between indices of circulating blood cells and bone homeostasis in osteoporosis. *Front Endocrinol.* 2022;13:965290.

[28] Saleem AM, Alsayed LM, Ahmed IA, Rezk NA. Biochemical markers and radiological findings in premature osteopenic neonates. *Egypt J Hosp Med.* 2022;87:2038–2045.

[29] Angelika D, Ugrasena IDG, Etika R, Rahardjo P, Bos AF, Sauer PJJ. The incidence of osteopenia of

prematurity in preterm infants without phosphate supplementation: a prospective, observational study. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2021;100(18):e25758. doi: 10.1097/MD.00000000000025758

[30] Zhang H, Jia Q, Piao M, Chang Y, Zhang J, Tong X, et al. Screening of serum alkaline phosphatase and phosphate helps early detection of metabolic bone disease in extremely low birth weight infants. *Front Pediatr.* 2021;9:642158.

[31] Paul SP, Das PK, Shaha D, Miah M, Akhter RJ, Hoque M, et al. Role of biochemical parameters for the detection of osteopenia of prematurity. *North Int Med Coll J.* 2024;13(1):581–587. doi: 10.3329/nimcj.v13i1.73544

[32] Rayannavar A, Calabria AC. Screening for metabolic bone disease of prematurity. *Semin Fetal Neonatal Med.* 2020;25(1):101086.

[33] Burr DB, Allen MR, editors. *Basic and Applied Bone Biology*. 2nd ed. Cambridge (MA): Academic Press; 2019. 478 p. doi:10.1016/C2018-0-04059-2

[34] Kurdi B, Nimeri N, Alomar S, Greer B, Abu Bakr A, et al. Evaluating the link between cord gas parameters and Apgar scores in high-risk pregnancies: insights from a one-year study in Qatar. *Research Square* [preprint]. 2023. doi:10.21203/rs.3.rs-3307739/v1

